

RESPONSE PAPER**LAST NAME: AGHADIUNO****FIRST NAME: MABEL****PROGRAM CODE: PHGH****COURSE CODE: ACA-401D****PERIOD NUMBER: 1****INSTRUCTOR: GULMA**

The author applied UK conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics

The student must use Turabian/Chicago parenthetical/in-text references (ideally with Zotero) and confirm below:

The author did use Zotero to insert references

The author did use Grammarly Premium

My plagiarism rate is 1%

The author used the following software: (MSWord 2019 on Windows 11)

List your seven key concepts with page number in text (then bold these terms in your RP)(samples below):

1. Introduction to Academic Essay Writing (Cleenewerck & Gulma 2021, 6-12)
2. Essay Organisation (Cleenewerck & Gulma 2021, 7-10)
3. Researching the Topic (Cleenewerck & Gulma 2021, 8)
4. UK v US English (Cleenewerck & Gulma 2021, 24-28)
5. Citation (Cleenewerck & Gulma 2021, 34-36)
6. CMS Crib Sheet (Cleenewerck & Gulma 2021, 43-56)
7. Conclusion

ESSENTIAL EQUIPMENT FOR THE ACADEMIC WRITING JOURNEY

1) INTRODUCTION

The ACA-401D course pack, fourth edition, that Cleenewerck and Gulma have revised is a seventy-two-page document providing a wide panorama of the definition and components of academic writing. The main aim of the module is to equip the student with the basics ‘of essay writing, punctuation, plagiarism’ (Cleenewerck & Gulma 2021, 3). The authors give time to the differentiation between UK and US English and stress the importance of being consistent in the use of style and the choice of the version of English. There are sections devoted to styles of writing, Latin abbreviations and a sample response paper. The topics range in diversity from the placement of the period (aka full stop) to ‘ethnolects’.

Put simply, the module presents the dos and don’ts of academic writing. As well as presenting the discipline of academic writing, the paper gives tips on choosing research topics, formulating research questions, researching and writing. It encourages students to familiarise

themselves with the strategy used by tutors to review papers. The detail at times is painstaking but it is given as essential for writing to fit into the academic genre.

2) **ESSAY ORGANISATION**

Since primary school, I have always liked writing. The school curriculum has changed over the years with targets and performance used to judge success. I suspect less time is devoted to the essay. At school, the essay only needed a beginning, middle and end. I liked the liberty of enthusing about a topic, did not worry about providing quotes and then gave the conclusion that satisfied me – its author. After all, the main requirement for my teacher was an interesting subject. The ACA-401D course pack explains that an ‘academic essay seeks to provide answers to hypotheses, aiming to communicate ideas based on evidence’ (Cleenewerck & Gulma, 2021 7). It takes the essay along another route that is rocky and steep. Communicating ideas based on evidence and adhering to strict guidelines is like being careful where I place my feet along a mountain path.

The authors advise against procrastination and advocate starting early. I would reduce this section of their paper to a mantra: read, research, reflect and ‘rite. The pyramid in Figure 1 of Cleenewerck & Gulma (2021, 8) gives the basic steps on academic essay writing. The picture reminds me of the well-known pyramid illustrating Maslow’s hierarchy of needs. Maslow places our physiologic needs at the base of the pyramid because they are essential, whereas the requirement for self-actualisation is at its peak. In the course pack’s pyramid, analysing the question and defining the key terms is at the base. However, before examining the question, I think even more fundamental is to establish the question. I think that should be at the base of the pyramid and not analysing the question.

I suppose writing an essay on a topic where I cannot identify a question or even have no interest in finding an answer will be challenging. Observing the world around me is crucial and asking the questions that follow. In the 1600s Sir Isaac Newton formulated the theory of gravity after watching an apple fall. His observation made him wonder why the apple plummeted straight down and not in another direction. I hope this course will challenge me to ask deeper questions of what I observe in practice, in the world of health so that I can formulate hypothesis.

3) **RESEARCHING THE TOPIC**

Cleenewerck and Gulma advise on the importance of researching the topic to provide a thesis and an answer to the question. They state that essay writing requires both creative and critical thinking (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2021, 9). I like the advice to collect evidence that supports a hypothesis and to gather evidence that refutes if it exists. A few months ago, I wrote a creative piece on the theme of climate change, postulating that it was bringing tropical disease to temperate climates. The idea of global warming and human culpability has gained greater acceptance worldwide. However not everyone agrees. If I had been writing an academic paper instead of creative fiction, I would have been obliged to trawl through

research debunking the idea of human culpability in global warming. A paper encompassing both viewpoints would be stimulating and certainly thought-provoking.

Research demands that I approach a subject free from bias so that I present opposing views with fairness. Strategies such as building up a case against the hypothesis will help. The authors give suggestions such as brainstorming and mapping. I think I will find these types of strategies helpful.

There is a plethora of information on the internet. A fallacy is mistaken for truth. Contradictory posts circulate on YouTube about how to manage just about anything, from losing weight to treating COVID.

Cleenewerck and Gulma do not suggest reliable sources for doing research. This may be because students at Euclid come from diverse disciplines which use varied search tools. The building blocks for the essay writing process are fundamental, so this explains the focus on the process. Recommended search engines and websites could have been added to the paper, but I suspect those topics will be covered later. Nonetheless, even reputable journals have to retract research papers as happened in the article linking autism to the MMR vaccine (Wakefield et al. 1998).

4) UK V US ENGLISH

In chapter three, Cleenewerck and Gulma focus on the difference between American and British English. This chapter exposed my ignorance. It was like facing the ‘not known to self’ part of the Johari window. I pride myself on being particular about spelling. I ensure my MS Word and other MS Office applications are set to British English. British spelling and word choices are easier. I have always written ‘colour’ instead of ‘color’. I do speak of ‘trousers’ and not ‘pants’ when I describe the clothes of a man slaloming through a busy crowd. However, it was sobering to realise that my use of quotation marks – proudly inserting the full stop (aka period) before the quotation marks - is American English. I did not know that in British English, the positioning of the full stop before or after the quotation mark varies (Cleenewerck, Laurent and Gulma, Kabiru 2021). Then there is the quotation within the quotation. In American English, a single inverted comma signals the inner source, while British English uses quotation marks. I must unlearn my current practice so my use of British English is consistent.

English is the common language in Nigeria – supposedly British English. Nigeria was a British colony. At first, the brazen use of American English in some public buildings with notices including words such as ‘health center’ or ‘tonite’, annoyed me. I did not like the lack of uniformity as I thought it could only create confusion, especially where English is not the first language, and children are trying to learn it. However, since reflecting on this topic, I have more understanding and tolerance.

The authors state that American English is spoken by more people than British English. I wonder if that is and always will be the case (Cleenewerck & Gulma 2021, 25). Indian English is mainly based on British English – although it contains many American

words. Then there are the millions in the countries of the former British colonies which supposedly learn British English.

The wealth of the US and its influence on mass media, politics and economy, its larger population are among the many reasons given for the predominance of American English. The power of the publishing industry in promulgating American English especially interested me (Cleenewerck & Gulma 2021). Authors like Jane Austen and Charlotte Bronte did not write in American English, yet I wondered what version of English is used by publishers such as Kindle or Kobo. Do they use British or American punctuation marks?

The genie has flown from the bottle. The world has grown smaller. Influence passes in an instant defying borders and miles. I ask myself if Euclid's insistence on consistently using American or British English is essential today, given that we use such a mishmash of English and punctuation and grammar in everyday life – even in Academic circles. Life would certainly be easier if we did not bother.

5) CITATION AND PLAGIARISM

Plagiarism is presenting someone else's work or ideas as your own. It is not confined to academic writing. On the first night of the Republican Convention in 2016, Melania Trump spoke words echoing those of Michelle Obama eight years previously. Initially, there were strenuous denials from the Trump camp. Subsequently, the speechwriter 'confessed' (Reuters 2016). Over the years, musicians in the pop industry have taken out plagiarism cases against other artists. The best defence against wittingly or unwittingly being accused or practising plagiarism is to credit the author and source.

However, I find the whole exercise of adding citations, entering quotation marks, referencing, and bibliography lists tedious. Essays I have written have been returned to enter the references correctly because I have not been always scrupulous about citing the correct page numbers, edition of the publication or the authors initial. Reading the chapter on plagiarism made me realise I have been using a mixture of reference styles (Chicago interchangeably and others) without appreciating there was a difference between them. I am grateful tools such as Zotero exist to make this task easier although I will need to give myself time to become proficient at using it.

6) CMS CRIB SHEET

The sixth chapter presents the Chicago Manual of Style (CMS) crib sheet. I think the CMS crib sheet (or similar aide depending on the preference of the academic institution) should be given to every student – undergrad or post – who has to write academic papers. It would have saved me much heartache and pain if I had such an item in the past. I note the Chicago Style recommends using Merriam-Webster's Collegiate Dictionary (Cleenewerck &

Gulma 2021, 44). I wondered if this was compatible with my choice to use British English and concluded that if Euclid gives us the option it must be possible.

The CMS crib sheet is divided into three sections covering the Chicago Style & its usage, page formatting and endnotes & footnotes. There are rules about compound words, capitalisation and abbreviations. I find it confusing when geographical terms such as South and North are capitalised in one context and not in another. The explanation given in the crib sheet seems to make sense (Cleenewerck & Gulma 2021, 46).

I like italics. I like the way they emphasise a word, especially when it is written. According to the CMS, I must be attentive to italics appropriately – at least in academic writing (Cleenewerck & Gulma 2021). This contradicts somewhat what I read in the second edition of the Oxford Dictionary of English Grammar where it says italics are used to ‘indicate words, phrases etc that require highlighting’ (Aarts 2014, ix). The Dictionary even allows the use of underlined italics ‘to highlight particular (or other elements) for attention’ (Aarts 2014, ix).

There are many other little pearls in crib sheet I found the answers to many questions I have been asked or asked myself about grammar and style since learning to hold a pen.

7) CONCLUSION

My first reaction on reviewing the course pack was dismay at the detailed, minutiae of academic writing. I despaired of remembering the fine detail, implementing the guidelines and comfortably using them without marring the flow of creativity. *Why Writing Matters* is an interesting book written by a group of authors from different parts of the world who explore advances in academic writing. In chapter four, Hamilton and Pitt question the very genre of academic writing, likening it to a ‘straightjacket’ that seeks to ‘centralise and perhaps stifle individual voices’ (in Carter n.d., 76) .

I admit at times, I find some academic writing dull and heavy. Writing this paper made me reflect on the contents of the course pack more. I now see the course pack as a vast, necessarily lengthy aide-memoir to bring out the best of academic writing so that it benefits not just me but others. The course pack does provide the student with the basics of academic writing. Now it is down to me to implement them. Mountain paths run through steep terrain, and you can get lost if you veer from them. The paths and signposts are always there for a reason.

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